

3 replications (see table). In the transplanted field, either carbofuran 3G at 0.681 kg ai/ha or diazinon 10G at 1.7 kg ai/ha was incorporated at final land preparation, and broadcast at maximum

tillering and panicle initiation. RTV infection was visually recorded at 70 d after transplanting.

Disease score (percentage and severity) was significantly lower in

carbofuran-treated plots than in diazinon-treated ones. It was lowest when carbofuran was applied in the seedbed and in transplanted plots up to panicle initiation. □

Mass rearing of *Nephotettix malayanus*

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Mass rearing techniques for the green leafhoppers *N. virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *N. cincticeps* have been successfully developed. However, no mass rearing technique has been developed for *N. malayanus*. Tests to select a host plant for *N. malayanus* rearing identified the weed *Leersia hexandra* as the most favorable. We developed a rearing procedure using *L. hexandra* (see fire).

L. hexandra cuttings were prepared by cutting 15-cm side shoots and transplanting them in pots at 10 cuttings/spot. Plants were fertilized with ammonium sulfate at 7 d after transplanting (DT). At 10 DT, 6 pots were placed in the oviposition cage. To start the culture, 100 field-collected females and 100 males were placed in the oviposition cage with the *L. hexandra* plants.

The 6 pots infested with eggs were transferred into the rearing cage and replaced with 6 new potted *L. hexandra* plants at 3 d-intervals. Eggs in the leaf sheaths of *L. hexandra* hatched in 8-10 d. Nymphs reached the 2d and 3d instar in 11-16 d, 4th and 5th in 17-21 d, and adulthood in 22-25 d. Fresh *L. hexandra* plants were placed in the cage each week. About 2,000-3,000 *N. malayanus* individuals can be produced in each generation with 1 oviposition cage and 1 rearing cage. Insects are maintained in the rearing cage until they are needed for varietal screening, insecticide screening,

N. malayanus rearing procedure and use of reared insects, IRRI.

studies on resistance mechanisms and tungro virus infection, or to maintain the

culture by transferring adults to the oviposition cage. □

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